

Impact of circular economy on Sustainability of agriculture in Karnataka with special reference to Shivamogga district-An analysis

Prepared by

Dr. Dhakshayani M. Dongre. MA., LLB.,M.phil., ph.d
Associate Professor and coordinator in PG Studies in Economics
Sri Sri Shivalingeshwara Swamy Government First Grade College
Channagiri – 577213
Davanagere District
Karnataka
IEA's Life No. – KA – 038

Abstract

Agriculture is a backbone of Indian economy, providing livelihoods for a significant portion of the population. The Tenth Five-Year Plan notably promoted organic farming, recognizing the rising global demand for organic produce and the premium prices it commands. India, with its relatively low use of chemical fertilizers—especially in rain-fed, north eastern, and hilly regions—has a promising opportunity to enhance organic food production for both export and local consumption. Initiatives to convert agricultural and municipal waste into organic compost have supported this growth, alongside increased financial backing from commercial and rural banks aimed at facilitating the transition to organic farming. India generates a huge quantity of agricultural waste. Immediate disposal of this agricultural waste can lead to loss of their probable economic value. However, by adopting circular economy, the agricultural waste can be reduced as it focuses on recycling and reuse of wastes to prevent the economic loss. A strategy known as circularity in agriculture tries to shut resource loops within the agricultural system, minimizing waste and maximizing resource efficiency. It entails developing farming methods and systems that reflect natural cycles, lessen reliance on finite resources, and support sustainable and regenerative practices. This article examines the impact of circular economy on sustainability of agriculture in Karnataka and its role in maintaining ecological balance.

Key words : circular economy in India boosts organic farming and ecological balance.

Introduction

Agriculture serves as the backbone of the Indian economy, accounting for the primary source of income for about 63% of the population, including 60% in Karnataka. As a vital sector for employment, agricultural development is integral to the nation's overall economic progress. The Tenth Five-Year Plan significantly advanced organic farming, responding to the growing global appetite for organic food. India's minimal reliance on chemical fertilizers positions it favourably to expand its organic food production for both export and domestic markets. India generates a huge quantity of agricultural waste. Immediate disposal of this agricultural waste can lead to loss of their probable economic value. However, by adopting circular economy, the agricultural waste can be reduced as it focuses on recycling and reuse of wastes to prevent the economic loss. Circularity offers an opportunity for agriculture to continue growing in a way that is both sustainable and profitable. By adopting circular principles that meet customers' expectations, leverage waste outputs to diversify revenue streams, mitigate vulnerable supply chains and create on-farm efficiencies, agricultural organizations can transform themselves to prioritize sustainability while optimizing outcomes. Small changes escalate into significant impacts. Reducing food waste alone has the potential to bring up to \$405 billion to businesses by 2030 all while reducing carbon emissions and better supporting environmental recovery and restoration. Circular economy will decelerate the depletion of natural resources and lower the environmental damages. India generates a huge quantity of agricultural waste. Immediate disposal of this agricultural waste can lead to loss of their probable economic value. However, by adopting circular economy, the agricultural waste can be reduced as it focuses on recycling and reuse of wastes to prevent the economic loss. The agricultural waste can be utilized as resources for other processes to improve their value. This chapter attempts to discuss the role of circular economy on agriculture, valorisation of agricultural waste, and the effective management strategies to reduce agricultural waste. It also highlights the various challenges to agricultural waste management and adaptation potentiality of circular economy in India. The concept of circularity offers just one way that the agricultural sector can reorganize itself to optimize both business outcomes and global impact.

Understanding circular economy A circular economy in agriculture is a model that aims to minimize waste, close the loop on resource use, and maximize value. This can be achieved by reusing, recycling, and repurposing materials and by products throughout the product's lifecycle. Geissdoerfer, M. Paulo, S. Nancy M.P.B, and Hultink E.J. (2017) defined circular economy as "a recovering system in which resource input and waste, emission, and energy leaks are curtailed by slowing, closing and reducing material and energy loops" a circular economy can be achieved through durable design, maintenance, repair, reuse, remanufacturing, refurbishing and recycling.

An integrated organic farming follows the 5R: Reduction of input, Reuse of agricultural Residues, Recycle water, Refuse inorganic fertiliser and pesticides, and R Replace of conventional practices with closer to nature practices. For an efficient circular economy, agriculture should be taken as a primary sector with sustainability as its prerequisite, forming the fundamental of the economy and the living system involved. A strategy known as circularity in agriculture tries to shut resource loops within the agricultural system, minimizing waste and maximizing resource efficiency. It entails developing farming methods and systems that reflect natural cycles, lessen reliance on finite resources, and support sustainable and regenerative practices. According to FAO, around one-third of all food produced for human consumption is lost or wasted globally, amounting to approximately 1.3 billion metric tonnes per year.

Today when resource scarcity and environmental concerns are becoming increasingly pressing, concept of circularity has gained significant attention. An economic model known as the "circular economy" seeks to reduce waste, increase resource efficiency, and advance sustainability. The old linear economy, which has a "take-make-dispose" structure, is sought to be replaced with one that closes the loop by preserving resources for as long as possible.

Agriculture being one of the largest users of natural resources and contributors to environmental impact, holds immense potential for circular practices. Circular agriculture focuses on optimizing resource utilization, minimizing waste and fostering sustainable food production. In this blog we delve into the concept of circularity in agriculture, exploring its principles, benefits and innovative approaches that are transforming the way we produce and consume food.

SAMPLING DESIGN

In this research study, simple random sampling method has been adopted. Simple random sampling of 100 respondents were interviewed and response were collected. From each taluk a sample of 20 respondents have been selected randomly. While selecting the beneficiaries, it was kept in view the respondents from different age groups/Income level / Education level / land holding .

Objectives of the Study

1. To emphasize the importance of circular economy in karnataka.
2. To analyze the different types circular agricultural practices.
3. To outline the characteristics of circular agriculture.
4. To examine challenges of circular economy.

Hypotheses of the Study

- Farmers do not utilise benefits of circular agricultural practices fully.
- Demand for organic farming is low .
- Awareness level of farmers about circular economy is low.

Analysis Techniques

Data collected for this study were analyzed using statistical methods. Tables were created for interpretation, and statistical tools such as percentages, averages, and Chi-square tests were employed to test the hypotheses.

Chi-square Test Formula:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{\sum (O-E)^2}{E}$$

Where, χ^2 = Chi – square value

O = Observed frequencies

E = Expected frequencies

Period of the study: the present study was conducted during 2023-24

Limitations

1. The study is focussed only impact of circular economy on sustainability of agriculture in Karnataka .
2. The present study is limited to 5 selected Taluks of Shivamogga Distrist.
3. Respondents are hesitant provide the necessary information, only 100 respondents are selected.

Importance of circular economy

As the population grows, stabilizing and enhancing agricultural production sustainably becomes imperative. Maintaining ecological balance is crucial for the survival of both human life and the environment. The reliance on agrochemicals, derived from non-renewable fossil fuels, poses economic and environmental challenges that necessitate a shift toward sustainable practices. A circular economy can help make agriculture in Karnataka more sustainable by reducing waste, using resources more efficiently, and minimizing environmental impact:

- **Reduce waste:** Circular economy practices like reusing, recycling, and repurposing materials and by products can help reduce waste.
- **Use resources more efficiently:** Circular economy practices can help farmers use resources more efficiently, which can lower input costs and boost output.
- **Minimize environmental impact:** Circular economy practices can help farmers reduce their environmental impact by using fewer harmful chemicals and practices.
- **Improve soil health:** Practices like crop rotation and composting can help improve soil health.
- **Promote biodiversity:** Practices like integrated pest management can help promote biodiversity.
- **Increase economic sustainability:** Circular economy practices can help smallholder farmers increase their financial success and long-term viability.

- **Reduce greenhouse gas emissions:** Circular economy practices can help reduce total annual greenhouse gas emissions.

A circular economy is a strategy for economic growth that aims to benefit the environment, society, and industry. It's based on the principles of reuse, reduce, recycle, refurbish/repair, and remanufacture.

Benefits of circular agriculture

Reduced waste and pollution

A more ecologically friendly and sustainable agricultural system is made possible through circular agriculture by minimizing waste output, improving resource usage, and lowering pollution. It contributes to the preservation of natural resources, lessens the negative effects of agriculture on ecosystems, and promotes the general welfare of both people and the environment.

Improved soil health.

Circular agriculture practices that improve soil health improve soil fertility, nutrient availability, water retention, and microbial activity. A sustainable agricultural output depends on healthy soils because they promote plant growth, increase crop resistance to pests and diseases, and support plant growth. Furthermore, by functioning as a carbon sink and trapping carbon dioxide from the atmosphere, healthy soils help to mitigate climate change.

Increased biodiversity.

Circular agriculture increases ecosystem resilience, pest and disease control, and overall ecological balance by fostering biodiversity. Pollination services, healthy soil, clean water, and the long-term viability of agricultural systems are all benefits of biodiversity in agricultural environments. Aside from supporting cultural and recreational activities, the existence of various habitats and species improves the aesthetic value of agricultural landscapes.

Increased resilience to climate change'

Circular agriculture assists farmers in adapting to the effects of climate change, lowering risks, and maintaining agricultural productivity in the face of shifting climatic conditions. By

assuring food security and the ability of farming communities to support themselves, it supports the general sustainability and long-term viability of agricultural systems.

Enhanced food security.

Food systems may become more productive, robust, and sustainable by implementing circular agriculture ideas and practises, which will ultimately improve food security on a local, national, and international scale. Circular agriculture promotes the availability, affordability, and accessibility of wholesome food, enhancing the livelihoods and general well-being of communities all over the world.

Economic benefits for farmers.

In general, circular agriculture boosts the economy by enhancing resource efficiency, lowering input costs, boosting output, gaining access to specialized markets, and fostering resilience. Small farmers can increase their financial success, long-term viability, and economic sustainability in a changing agricultural environment by implementing circular practices.

Types of circular agricultural practices

Agro forestry

The practice of circular agriculture includes agroforestry. It is a crucial element that supports the resilience and sustainability of agricultural systems.

Agro forestry within circular agriculture practices improves biodiversity, soil health, climate resilience, and economic potential by incorporating trees into agricultural landscapes. By maximizing resource utilization, enhancing ecosystem processes, and assisting resilient and sustainable agricultural systems, it serves as an excellent example of circularity.

Crop rotation

It is one of the circular agriculture practices that farmers can use to better manage pests, nutrient cycling, soil health, and risk. It promotes long-term sustainability, lessens dependency on chemical inputs, and supports resilient and effective agricultural systems.

Composting

Composting is an efficient and sustainable circular agriculture practice that promotes waste reduction, improved soil health, and overall agricultural system sustainability. It encourages

more resource-saving and regenerative farming techniques, supports nutrient recycling, and lessens its negative environmental effects.

Organic farming

Agronomic practices that emphasize producing crops and livestock without the use of synthetic chemicals, genetically modified organisms (GMOs), or artificial additions are known as organic farming. It is founded on ideas that support healthy soil, biodiversity, ecological balance, and resource management that is sustainable.

Regenerative agriculture

It is a comprehensive and systems-based method of farming with the objective of regenerating the ecosystem services and natural resources essential to agriculture. By actively reviving the soil and encouraging cyclical cycles of growth and renewal, it goes beyond sustainable practices. Regenerative agriculture offers the possibility for sustainable and regenerative food production systems by placing a priority on soil health, biodiversity, and climate resilience.

Characteristics of circular agriculture

The principal characteristics of circular agriculture are as follows:

- In keeping with the principles of resource conservation, it emphasises improving the production environment and protecting farmland biodiversity as the foundation of stable, sustainable development. The circular agriculture framework embraces an industrial approach to agriculture management, stressing clean production practices, technological improvements and the use of environmentally friendly 'green' agro-chemicals so as to minimise environmental impact.
- It applies technology to optimise the structural order of agricultural systems, organising production according to the feedback model of: resources- -product -waste - recycled resources, thus obtaining the maximum utility from resources committed.
- It extends the eco-industrial chain of agriculture by encouraging the reutilisation of wastes, elemental coupling, etc. in conjunction with related industries, thereby fostering production networks and collaborative development.
- By encouraging 'clean' and conservation-minded lifestyles in rural communities, it promotes a beneficial modern culture.

SECTION – I SOCIO – ECONOMIC PROFILE OF THE BENEFICIARIES

Sample Respondents

Simple random sampling method was used for surveying the respondents. The number of sample respondents interviewed and response were collected. The data has been collected from the 100 sample respondents 20 respondents have been selected from each selected taluks.

Table – 1 represents the sample respondents interviewed. A total of 100 respondents were interviewed from different taluka out of which the sample respondents of 20 (20 percent) were interviewed in each taluk of Shimoga, Shikaripura, Bhadravathi, Sagara and Soraba.

Table – 1
Sample respondents Interviewed

Taluks	No. Of respondents
Shimoga	20 (20)
Shikaripura	20 (20)
Bhadravathi	20 (20)
Sagara	20 (20)
Soraba	20 (20)
Total	100 (100)

Source : Survey data.

Note : Figures in the brackets represent percentage

From the above table, it is clear that equal numbers of respondents are from five taluks in the district.

Age Wise :

The respondents were classified in to three age groups viz., 45 years, 45 to 60 years and above 60 years. Table 2 indicates that a large number of respondents (66 percent) belong

to age group below the age group of 45 years. It is followed by age group 45 – 60 years (28 percent) and above 60 years (6 percent)

Table – 2
Age – Wise Classification of Sample Respondents Interviewed

Taluks	Age Groups			
	Up to 45	45 – 60	60 and above	Total
Shimoga	17(85)	3 (15)	00	20 (100)
Shikaripura	16 (80)	4 (20)	00	20 (100)
Bhadravathi	10 (50)	8(40)	02 (10)	20 (100)
Sagara	15(75)	5(25)	00	20 (100)
Soraba	14(70)	4 (20)	02(10)	20 (100)
Total	72 (72)	24 (24)	4(4)	100 (100)

Source : Survey data.

Note : Figures in the brackets represent percentage

Education - wise

Education wise, the respondents surveyed and have been divided into four educational categories viz., illiterate, primary, High school to PUC & Degree and above.

Table – 3
Education level of Sample Respondents

Taluks	Illiterate	Primary	High School to PUE	Degree & above
Shimoga	2(10)	5(25)	10 (50)	3 (15)
Shikaripura	4(20)	3 (15)	10 (50)	3(15)
Bhadravathi	2 (10)	4 (20)	13 (65)	1 (5)
Sagara	02(10)	5 (25)	10(50)	3 (15)
Soraba	0	4 (20)	12(60)	4(20)
Total	10 (10)	21(21)	55 (55)	14 (14)

Source : Survey data

Note : Figures in the brackets represent percentage

Table 3 Indicates that highest percentage of respondents in the sample had education up to high school level i.e., 60 percent ; out of 100 respondents, 20 percent of the respondents had studied primary, 10 percent of sample respondents are illiterate, 21 percent had studied primary education and 14 percent had studied up to degree and level.

Land holding pattern

Land holding is used as one of the important economic indicator of sample respondents, it would be better to know the land holding pattern of the beneficiaries. The respondents are categorised in to three groups on the basis if land holding in acres. They are, those who are holding land up to 2.5 acres (marginal farmers), 2.5 – 5 acres (small farmers) and above 5 acres (Large farmers).

Table – 4
Taluks wise Land Holding Pattern of Sample Respondents

Banks/taluks	Up to 2.5 acres (M.F.)	2.5 – 5 acres S.F.	Above 5 acres (L.F)	Total
Shimoga	5(25)	10 (50)	5(25)	20 (100)
Shikaripura	5(25)	13 (65)	2 (10)	20 (100)
Bhadravathi	6 (30)	12(60)	2(10)	20 (100)
Sagara	01(5)	15(75)	4(20)	20 (100)
Soraba	7 (35)	10(50)	3 (15)	20 (100)
Total	24 (24)	60 (60)	16 (16)	100 (100)

Source : Survey data

Note : Figures in the brackets represent percentage

MF = Marginal farmers, S.F = Small farmers

And LF = Large farmers

SECTION : II

UTILISATION OF BENEFITS OF CIRCULAR AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES

The section reveals the Farmers do not utilise benefits of circular agricultural practices fully. Many respondents do not utilise the benefits of circular agricultural practices for the said purposes most of large farmers have fully utilised compared to small farmers.

Table – 5
Utilisation of benefits of circular agricultural practices

Utilisation / Respondents	Fully utilized	Partially utilized	Total
Large farmers	75 (93.75)	05 (6.25)	80 (100)
Small farmers	05 (25)	15 (75)	20 (100)
Total	80 (80)	20 (20)	100 (100)
Chi-square test : $\chi^2 = 0.956$; d. f = 1 : significant at 5% level			

Source : Survey data

Note : Figures in brackets represent percentage

Table-5 revealed that there is a difference between large and small farmers and large farmers are utilizing more benefits of circular agriculture . Out of 100 respondents, 80 (80 percent) respondents are fully utilized and 20 (20 percent) respondents are partially utilized. 75 (93.75 percent) of large farmers are fully utilized and 5 (6.25 percent) respondents are partially utilized.

- The Chi-square test of significance is applied for the testing the hypothesis “Farmers do not utilise benefits of circular economy practices.” This hypothesis accepted because the calculated value is 0.956 which is less than the table value 3.84 at 5% level of significance (degrees of freedom is 1).

Conclude that utilization of benefits of circular agricultural practices is very low. compared to the small farmers.

DEMAND FOR ORGANIC FARMING

Demand for organic farming is low. This hypothesis is accepted .

Table – 6
Opinions of Respondents

Opinion / Sectors	High Demand	Low Demand	Total
Organic farming	5 (25)	15(75)	20 (100)
Conventional farming	70(87.5)	10(12.5)	80 (100)
Total	75 (75)	25 (25)	100 (100)
Chi – square test : $\chi^2 = 0.909$; $d.f = 1$: no significant at 5 % level			

Source : Survey data

Note : Figures in Brackets represent percentage.

Table – 6 indicated that the There is a high Demand for conventional farming, because 70 respondents demanded and 10 demanded less “Demand for organic farming is low” This hypothesis is accepted by applying Chi-Squat test, because calculated value is 0.909 which is less than the table value 3.841 at 5% level of significance. (d.f = 1)

Awareness level of farmers

Awareness level of farmers about circular agriculture is low

Table – 7

Awareness level	high	low	Total
Large farmers	80 (88.8)	10 (11.1)	90 (100)
Small farmers	06 (60)	04 (40)	10 (100)
Total	86 (86)	14 (14)	100 (100)
Chi – square test : $\chi^2 = 0.684$; $d.f = 1$: significant at 5 % level			

Source : Survey data.

Note : Figures in the brackets represent percentage.

Note : Figures in the brackets represent percentage.

Table –7 revealed that awareness level in large farmers is very high that is 80 when compared to the small farmers that is 06. This Hypothesis is accepted because calculated value is 0.684 which is less than the table value 3.841 at 5% level of significance.

Major Findings

- There is a difference between large and small farmers and large farmers are utilizing more benefits of circular agriculture . Out of 100 respondents, 80 (80 percent) respondents are fully utilized and 20 (20 percent) respondents are partially utilized. 75 (93.75 percent) of large farmers are fully utilized and 5 (6.25 percent) respondents are partially utilized.

The Chi-square test of significance is applied for the testing the hypothesis “Farmers do not utilise benefits of circular economy practices.” This hypothesis accepted because the calculated value is 0.956 which is less than the table value 3.84 at 5% level of significance (degrees of freedom is 1).

Conclude that utilization of benefits of circular agricultural practices is very low. compared to the small farmers.

- There is a high Demand for conventional farming, because 70 respondents demanded and 10 demanded less “Demand for organic farming is low” This hypothesis is accepted by applying Chi-Squat test, because calculated value is 0.909 which is less than the table value 3.841 at 5% level of significance. (d.f = 1)
- awareness level in large farmers is very high that is 80 when compared to the small farmers that is 06. This Hypothesis is accepted because calculated value is 0.684 which is less than the table value 3.841 at 5% level of significance.

Recommendations

- Enhance awareness about sustainability of circular agriculture.
- Increase loan availability for organic farming initiatives and boost organic farming
- Implement certified labelling for organic products to boost consumer demand.
- Foster awareness and education among farmers regarding circular agricultural practices .

- Ensure fair pricing for organic produce.
- Organize awareness campaigns by government support to sustain circular agriculture.
- Develop market mechanisms to evaluate land for organic farming.
- Promote dairy farming alongside organic agriculture.
- Enhance soil health through sustainable practices.

Conclusion

Agriculture being one of the largest users of natural resources and contributors to environmental impact, holds immense potential for circular practices. Circular agriculture focuses on optimizing resource utilization, minimizing waste and fostering sustainable food production. In this blog we delve into the concept of circularity in agriculture, exploring its principles, benefits and innovative approaches that are transforming the way we produce and consume food. Organic farming presents an environmentally friendly and economically viable approach to agriculture. While there is a growing demand for organic products, many farmers remain hesitant due to lower yields and limited access to organic inputs. The Organic Trade Association highlights that organic practices reduce pollutants in groundwater, enhance soil health, and diminish erosion, thus supporting sustainable plant growth. Moreover, organic farming typically requires 50% less energy than conventional methods.

References

- Agarwal, N.P. & Agarwal, S. (2006). Sampling Methods and Hypothesis Testing. RBSA Publishers.
- Balmohan Das, V., Prabhakar Rao, J.V., & Hrushikesavarao, P. (1991). Rural Banks and Rural Credit. Discovery Publications..
- Chakravarty, T.K. (1980). Development of Small and Marginal Farmers and Agricultural Labourers. National Institute of Rural Development.
- Chen Demin (2002), Xunhuan Nongye. Zhongguo Weilai Nongye de Fazhan Moshi. (Circular Agriculture – A Model for the Future of Agriculture in China), Jingjishi, No. 11, p. 134.
- Dubashi, P.R. (1985) Policy and Performance : Agriculture and Rural Development in Post Independence India, New Delhi : Stage Publications.
- Dwivedi, R.C (1972), New Strategy of Agriculture Development in India, Meerat : Oyall Book Depot.

- Etiema and Gilbert, Rural Development in India, New Delhi : Sage Publications, 1986.
- Geissdoerfer.M, Paulo, S. Nanacy.M.P.B and Hultink E.J (2017). The circular economy – a new sustainability paradigm? Clean prod.
- Ji Kunsen (2004), Xunhuan Jingji Yuanli yu Yingyong (Principles and Applications of Circular Economy), Anhui Scientific Publishing House, pp. 169-170.
- Ma Rong (2005), Deguo Xunhuan Jingji de Fazhan Gaikuang (Development of Circular Economy in Germany), Zhongguo Huanbao Chanye,5